

RESULTS OF DELAYED APPENDECTOMY AFTER TREATMENT OF APPENDICULAR INFILTRATE

¹Nishanov M.F., ²Ibragimova M.U.

^{1,2}Andijan State Medical Institute

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Abstract. *In the given article the authors made analysis regarding the implementation of delayed appendectomy in each compared groups since effective resorption of the infiltrate does not prevent relapses of acute appendicitis and in most cases, surgeons strongly recommend performing a planned operation to eliminate the etiologic factor.*

Keywords: *appendicular infiltrate, acute appendicitis, appendectomy, relapse, laser irradiation.*

Relevance. It is important to mention about the latest trends in the treatment of appendicular infiltrate (AI), many researchers still prefer conservative treatment followed by interval appendectomy. The spectrum of complex treatment is usually aimed at the use of antibiotic therapy to combat infection and reduce inflammation [7]. If the infiltrate is complicated by the formation of an abscess, percutaneous drainage is performed under ultrasound control. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs are used to reduce pain and inflammation [9].

It is known to everyone that bed rest can be recommended in the first days, especially with severe pain syndrome; after the inflammation has subsided, the patient is recommended to gradually activate in order to avoid the development of adhesions and improve recovery [8]. Some authors recommend the use of auxiliary local methods of influencing AI (ultrasound therapy, magnetic therapy, electrophoresis, thermal procedures, etc.) [5,6].

At the same time, the issues of using laser technologies in the treatment of AI are devoted to single publications. The first studies in this area showed good results, reflected in a reduction in the duration of inpatient treatment, a decrease in the number of abscesses [2]. The effectiveness of laser exposure is associated with a potential effect on pain syndrome and inflammation, as well as acceleration of regenerative processes in the affected area [1,3,4].

Objective. The main issue is improving the results of delayed appendectomy after appendicular infiltrate.

Materials and methods. In our study, 17 patients (33.3%) in the comparison group refrained from surgical treatment after successful treatment of AI. In the main group, 5 patients (12.5%) refused surgery. These patients were excluded from further analysis due to lack of contact with them. Also in the comparison group, emergency surgery without appendix removal was performed in 2 patients (4.8%), and emergency surgery with appendix removal was performed in 2 more patients (4.8%). Accordingly, delayed appendectomy in the comparison group was performed in 24 patients (57.1%) with successful treatment of AI and in 2 more patients with performed abscess drainage. In the main group, interval surgery was performed in 35 patients (87.5%).

Statistical analysis (chi-square) showed that the differences between the groups for this factor were significant ($\chi^2=8.881$; $df=3$; $p=0.031$), indicating a significant difference in treatment approaches between the groups (Table 1).

Results and discussion. The frequency of OA recurrence within 1 to 4 months after treatment with AI in the comparison group of 26 people was 19.2% (5 patients), in the main group

there was a relapse in only 2 patients (5.7%). The maximum period of delayed surgery in the comparison group was 16 weeks, the minimum - 1 week (all surgeries up to 2 months were performed for emergency indications due to relapse of OA clinical symptoms). The median (mean value) is 12 weeks. The mean value taking into account the standard deviation ($M \pm \delta$) is 11.9 ± 4.3 weeks. The confidence interval for the minimum value is 10.2 weeks, for the maximum - 14.1 weeks. In the main group, the maximum period of delayed surgery was also 16 weeks, but the minimum period in this group is longer - 4 weeks, which is due to the absence of OA relapse during these periods.

Table 1

Distribution of patients by type of final treatment of acute appendicitis complicated by AI

Treatment type	Comparison group		Main group	
	n	%	N	%
Conservative only AI	14	33,3%	5	12,5%
Emergency surgery for abscess development (without appendectomy)	2	4,8%	0	0,0%
Emergency surgery for abscess development (without appendectomy)	2	4,8%	0	0,0%
Delayed appendectomy	24	57,1%	35	87,5%
Total	42	100,0%	40	100,0%
χ^2	8,881; df=3; p=0,031			

The median was 6 weeks, indicating a shorter period of surgery compared to the comparison group. The mean value with standard deviation ($M \pm \delta$) in the main group was 6.7 ± 2.5 weeks. The confidence interval for the minimum value was 5.9 weeks, and for the maximum value, 8.0 weeks (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Time to perform delayed surgery ($M \pm \delta$; weeks)

It should be suggested that the statistical analysis showed a significant difference between the groups, with a t-value of 5.53 and a significance level of $p < 0.05$. This indicates that the time to perform delayed appendectomy was significantly shorter in the main group compared to the comparison group.

Besides that, it should be noted that performing delayed appendectomy after treatment with AI may be accompanied by a number of technical difficulties:

- After the inflammatory process and the formation of an infiltrate, adhesions may form, which complicate the isolation of the appendix and other anatomical structures, which increases the risk of damage to the intestine and other organs.
- As a result of inflammation and scarring, normal anatomical landmarks may change, which complicates the identification of the appendix and other important structures during surgery.
- The infiltrate and surrounding tissues may be more vascularized, which increases the risk of bleeding during surgery and requires more careful hemostasis.
- Tissues that were involved in the infiltrate may become denser and more fibrous, which complicates dissection and increases the time of the operation.
- Due to the inflammatory process, the walls of the appendix and surrounding structures may be weakened, which increases the risk of perforation of the appendix or adjacent organs.
- All these factors can significantly increase the duration of the operation, which increases the workload for the patient and the surgeon.

Definitely, these technical difficulties require a high level of training from the surgeon, the use of special instruments and, in some cases, the need to convert laparoscopic surgery to open surgery to ensure patient safety.

Analysis of the characteristics of the appendectomies performed showed that laparoscopic intervention without technical difficulties was only in 2 patients (7.7%) in the comparison group, while in 8 patients (22.9%) in the main group. Technical difficulties during laparoscopic surgery were noted in the comparison group in 3 patients (11.5%), in the main group - in 5 patients (14.3%), and conversion was performed in 2 of 3 and in 1 of the patients. Laparotomy without technical difficulties in the comparison group was performed in 9 patients (34.6%), while in the main group - 18 patients (51.4%). Laparotomic appendectomy with technical difficulties was performed in 12 patients (46.2%) in the comparison group, and in 4 patients (11.4%) in the main group. In total, statistical analysis showed a significant difference between the groups ($\chi^2=9.990$; $df=3$; $p=0.019$), indicating a difference in the distribution of types of operations and the presence of technical difficulties between the two groups (Table 2).

By summarizing these data, the following can be noted: The use of laser technologies in the complex treatment of AI in the main group significantly affected the outcomes of subsequent appendectomies, facilitating the performance of operations. In the main group, 74.3% of appendectomies were performed without technical complications, which is significantly higher compared to the comparison group (42.3%). At the same time, the proportion of operations with technical complications in the main group was significantly lower - 25.7% versus 57.7% in the comparison group. The use of laser technologies contributed to more effective treatment of AI, reducing the severity of the inflammatory process and reducing the volume of adhesions. This, in turn, led to a decrease in tissue density and vascularization, which facilitated access to the appendix, simplified its isolation and minimized the risk of damage to surrounding structures during surgery. Statistical analysis confirmed a significant difference between the groups

($\chi^2=6.392$; $df=1$; $p=0.012$), indicating a significant improvement in the conditions for performing delayed appendectomy in the main group due to the use of laser technologies (Fig. 2).

Table 2

Characteristics of appendectomies performed

Treatment type	Comparison group		Main group	
	N	%	n	%
Laparoscopically without technical difficulties	2	7,7%	8	22,9%
Laparoscopically with technical difficulties	3	11,5%	5	14,3%
Laparotomy without technical difficulties	9	34,6%	18	51,4%
Laparotomy with technical difficulties	12	46,2%	4	11,4%
Total	26	100,0%	35	100,0%
χ^2	9,990; $df=3$; $p=0,019$			

Fig. 2. Total proportion of complex appendectomies

According to the intraoperative technical difficulties, the frequency of postoperative complications also varied. In the comparison group, 15.4% of patients (4 patients) had wound suppuration, while in the main group this figure was significantly lower - 2.9% (1 patient). The frequency of wound infiltrate development was also lower in the main group (5.7%) compared to the comparison group (11.5%).

Bronchopulmonary complications in the form of pneumonia occurred in 15.4% of patients in the comparison group and only 2.9% in the main group. In total, the number of patients with complications was 30.8% (8) in the comparison group and only 8.6% (3) in the main group. Accordingly, 69.2% of patients in the comparison group (18) did not have postoperative complications, while in the main group this figure was significantly higher - 91.4% (32). Statistical analysis showed a significant difference between the groups ($\chi^2=4.973$; $df=1$; $p=0.026$), indicating that the incidence of postoperative complications was significantly lower in the main group (Table 3).

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested that the use of laser technologies in the complex treatment of AI in the main group allowed to significantly reduce the frequency of relapses of acute appendicitis (to 5.7% compared to 19.2% in the comparison group), and also to

reduce the time of delayed appendectomy to 6.7 ± 2.5 weeks versus 11.9 ± 4.3 weeks in the comparison group. In the main group, 74.3% of appendectomies were performed without technical difficulties (versus 42.3% in the comparison group), and the frequency of operations with technical difficulties was significantly lower (25.7% versus 57.7%), which is due to a decrease in the adhesion process and easier access to the appendix.

Table 3

Frequency of postoperative complications

Complication	Comparison group		Main Group	
	n	%	N	%
Wound suppuration	4	15,4%	1	2,9%
Wound infiltrate	3	11,5%	2	5,7%
Bronchopulmonary	4	15,4%	1	2,9%
Patients with complications	8	30,8%	3	8,6%
Without complications	18	69,2%	32	91,4%
χ^2	4,973; df=1; p=0,026			

The frequency of postoperative complications was also lower in the main group - 8.6% versus 30.8%, which included a decrease in cases of wound suppuration, wound infiltrate and bronchopulmonary complications. All improvements were statistically significant, confirming that laser technologies contribute to more effective and safe treatment of AI, simplify surgical interventions and reduce the risk of postoperative complications.

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